

SUPERSHINE

D6.4 – Report on dissemination and communication activities, including impact analysis

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Technical references

Project Acronym	SUPERSHINE
Project Title	S=Smart U=Upgraded asset-values and quality of life P=Public Private Partnership E=Extended Energy Efficiency R=Renewables triggered by the project SH=Social Housing I=Investment N=Net Zero E=European
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*

PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project’s page)

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1.2	23/03/2026	ICONS	Final draft sent to SC and PC for review
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1. Executive Summary

This report presents an overview of the communication and dissemination activities carried out within the project, including an assessment of their reach, effectiveness, and overall impact. It outlines the strategies adopted, the tools and channels implemented, and the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to monitor results throughout the project lifecycle.

Building on the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D6.1 and its update in D6.2), this document highlights the progress achieved in the implementation of the project's strategy and reflects the continuous efforts to maximise the visibility, accessibility, and uptake of SUPERSHINE results.

The communication and dissemination strategy was designed to ensure broad visibility of the project's objectives, activities, and results, while fostering engagement among key stakeholders. Strategic objectives focused on increasing awareness, promoting knowledge exchange, supporting replication potential, and contributing to policy and practice. A targeted approach was adopted to effectively reach diverse audiences, including policymakers, researchers, industry stakeholders, and the general public.

A mix of online channels and communication tools was deployed to maximize outreach. The project website served as the central hub for information, complemented by active use of social media platforms and dedicated campaigns to amplify visibility and engagement. In parallel, a wide range of dissemination materials was produced, including key outputs such as the policy brief, factsheets, and the final publication. In addition, several project partners were involved in video interviews, contributing to a more engaging and accessible presentation of project activities and results.

The project also placed strong emphasis on interactive and collaborative activities. The project coordinator, the scientific coordinator, and several partners actively participated in numerous events, both online and in presence, significantly contributing to the dissemination of project knowledge and results. These efforts were further strengthened through workshops, webinars, and clustering initiatives with sister projects, culminating in a final event that showcased key outcomes and encouraged stakeholder dialogue.

Monitoring and impact assessment were conducted through a structured framework, including website analytics, publication engagement metrics (PEI), and social media indicators (SEI). These tools enabled continuous tracking of performance and informed adjustments to improve effectiveness over time.

Overall, the communication and dissemination activities successfully contributed to achieving the project's objectives, demonstrating solid outreach, stakeholder engagement, and impact. The defined KPIs were largely met or exceeded, confirming the effectiveness of the adopted strategy and providing a strong foundation for future exploitation and scalability of project results.

2. Introduction

The main objective of SUPERSHINE was to accelerate the sustainable renovation of social housing across Europe by integrating technical optimisation, innovative financial schemes, and human-centred governance models. The project aimed to establish scalable and replicable frameworks enabling municipalities, housing providers and investors to implement economically viable and socially inclusive renovation strategies.

By combining building performance assessment, Public–Private Partnership (PPP) models, and district-level planning approaches, SUPERSHINE contributed to a paradigm shift in the social housing renovation value chain, aligning climate neutrality objectives with social equity and energy poverty reduction.

Communicating and disseminating the project’s objectives, activities and results to its targeted audiences was therefore a strategic priority. Effective communication ensured awareness among the public and local communities, while dissemination activities supported uptake among professional stakeholders, policymakers, financial actors and technical experts. These actions strengthened the exploitation potential of the project’s Key Exploitable Results, including the SUPERSHINE Toolkit, Financial Tool and replication blueprints.

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination activities carried out throughout the entire project duration, up to its conclusion. It describes the materials produced, the channels deployed, the stakeholder engagement strategies implemented, and the measurable results achieved in terms of outreach, engagement and impact.

A substantial part of the document is dedicated to the monitoring strategy implemented throughout the project lifecycle. Continuous monitoring of website analytics, social media performance, stakeholder engagement indicators and publication dissemination allowed for adaptive improvements in strategy and ensured alignment with project KPIs.

The data collected demonstrate a strong outreach performance and high levels of stakeholder engagement, confirming the relevance of SUPERSHINE’s approach and the growing interest in integrated, financially viable and socially inclusive renovation models for social housing across Europe.

2.1. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The SUPERSHINE project has successfully implemented and completed its Communication, Engagement and Dissemination (CED) strategy, based on complementary and mutually reinforcing approaches designed to maximise visibility, stakeholder uptake and long-term impact of the project’s results.

Communication activities aimed to increase visibility and awareness of SUPERSHINE’s objectives, activities, results, impacts and societal benefits among non-technical audiences and the general public.

Information was translated into accessible and clear messages to ensure broad understanding of how sustainable social housing renovation contributes to reduced energy bills, improved living conditions, climate neutrality and social inclusion. By presenting technical and financial innovations in an understandable manner, SUPERSHINE fostered public acceptance of renovation measures and strengthened awareness of the importance of addressing energy poverty through integrated solutions.

Communication efforts targeted citizens, tenants, local communities, media representatives and the broader public, contributing to the creation of social value around the project’s outcomes.

Dissemination activities aimed to facilitate the acceptance, adoption and replication of SUPERSHINE’s results among technical and professional audiences operating within the social housing, urban planning and financial ecosystems.

These efforts ensured the effective transfer of knowledge, methodologies and tools, including the SUPERSHINE Toolkit, Financial Tool, indicator framework and replication blueprints. Dissemination formats adopted a technical and formal tone of voice, providing detailed information on energy performance optimisation, Public–Private Partnership models, governance frameworks and financial feasibility assessments.

The primary dissemination targets included municipalities, social housing providers, public authorities, financial institutions, investors, energy agencies, researchers and policymakers. Through conferences, workshops, policy events, scientific publications and targeted stakeholder meetings, SUPERSHINE contributed to building a strong community of practice at European, national and local levels around sustainable and inclusive renovation of social housing.

Engagement activities focused on establishing structured and continuous two-way interaction with selected stakeholders, ensuring their active participation in project activities and validation processes.

This approach integrated stakeholders’ perspectives, needs and expectations into the development and refinement of SUPERSHINE solutions. Lighthouse Demonstrators and Fellow Cities played a central role in this process, enabling practical validation of technical and financial models in diverse regulatory and climatic contexts. Stakeholder engagement enhanced the relevance, feasibility and replicability of the project outcomes.

The Communication, Dissemination and Engagement strategy was closely aligned with exploitation objectives, promoting the uptake, scalability and sustainability of SUPERSHINE’s results beyond the

project's conclusion. The strategy operated simultaneously at European/international and local/regional/national levels.

At the European level, ICONS, as Communication and Dissemination leader, in close collaboration with the Project Coordinator and consortium partners, managed official project communication, ensured alignment with the Communication and Dissemination Plan, and coordinated external relations with European platforms, networks and institutional stakeholders.

At the local level, Lighthouse partners and other consortium members acted as key contact points with municipalities, housing providers, financial actors, policymakers and citizens, ensuring contextualised communication and targeted stakeholder interaction.

Throughout the entire project duration, a continuous monitoring and impact assessment process evaluated the performance and effectiveness of Communication, Dissemination and Engagement activities. Performance indicators, engagement indexes and KPI tracking provided structured feedback, allowing for the progressive refinement of the strategy and ensuring alignment with project objectives.

2.2. Strategic Objectives

The strategic objective of SUPERSHINE's Communication, Dissemination and Engagement (CED) strategy was to maximise the visibility, uptake, replication and long-term sustainability of the project's results, ensuring alignment with European climate, energy and social inclusion policies. More specifically, the CED strategy pursued the following objectives:

1. Raise Awareness and Build Social Acceptance

Increase awareness among citizens, tenants and local communities about the benefits of sustainable social housing renovation, highlighting improvements in energy efficiency, affordability, indoor comfort and environmental performance.

By translating technical and financial innovations into accessible messages, the strategy aimed to foster social acceptance of renovation interventions and reinforce public support for the energy transition in vulnerable housing segments.

2. Facilitate Uptake and Replication of Project Results

Promote the adoption of SUPERSHINE's Key Exploitable Results including the SUPERSHINE Toolkit, Financial Tool, indicator framework and replication blueprints among municipalities, housing providers and financial actors.

The strategy supported knowledge transfer and practical application, enabling stakeholders to integrate SUPERSHINE methodologies into local renovation planning and investment strategies.

3. Strengthen Stakeholder Networks and Build a Community of Practice

Establish and consolidate connections with European platforms, city networks, financial institutions, energy agencies and policy bodies.

Through targeted dissemination and engagement activities, SUPERSHINE contributed to building a community of practice around financially viable and socially inclusive renovation models for social housing.

This was further reinforced through active participation in workshops, conferences, and clustering activities, including collaboration with sister projects and EU initiatives, which supported knowledge exchange, strengthened synergies, and increased the visibility and uptake of project results.

4. Support Policy Alignment and Institutional Uptake

Ensure that project outcomes were positioned within the broader EU policy framework, including the European Green Deal, the Renovation Wave Strategy, the Energy Efficiency Directive and Climate City Contracts.

By engaging policymakers and public authorities, the CED strategy aimed to facilitate the integration of SUPERSHINE solutions into regulatory frameworks, funding schemes and long-term urban strategies.

5. Ensure Long-Term Sustainability Beyond the Project Duration

Align communication and dissemination activities with exploitation objectives to ensure continued use, scaling and further development of SUPERSHINE results after project completion.

This objective was supported through strategic targeting, performance monitoring and continuous adaptation of tools and channels.

2.3. Target Audience

SUPERSHINE identified and structured its target audiences through a detailed stakeholder mapping analysis, segmenting actors according to their role in enabling, financing, implementing, regulating or benefiting from sustainable social housing renovation.

The stakeholder categories targeted by the project, together with their relevance to SUPERSHINE, are presented in the table below.

Table 1: SUPERSHINE Target Audiences

Stakeholder Group	Sub-groups	Role and Relevance in SUPERSHINE
Policymakers and Public Authorities	European institutions and agencies; National governments; Local and regional authorities; Public regulatory and implementing bodies	These stakeholders play a decisive role in shaping regulatory frameworks, funding mechanisms, and long-term urban strategies. Engagement aimed to ensure alignment of SUPERSHINE results with EU climate and energy policies, including the European Green Deal,

Stakeholder Group	Sub-groups	Role and Relevance in SUPERSHINE
		Renovation Wave, and Energy Efficiency Directive.
Social Housing Organisations	Public providers of social housing; Private providers of social housing	This category represents the primary implementation layer of SUPERSHINE solutions. Social housing providers are central to the adoption of the Toolkit, Financial Tool, indicator framework, and replication guidelines. They were prioritised across all KERs (1–5), as they are directly concerned with the full spectrum of project innovations.
Financing Institutions	Local financing institutions; European financing institutions; Public and private investment actors	Financial stakeholders were engaged to validate and promote innovative Public–Private Partnership (PPP) schemes and to facilitate the mobilisation of capital for large-scale social housing renovation.
Construction and Building Industry	Construction and refurbishment service providers; Engineering companies; Technical consultants	This group supports the practical implementation of renovation measures and benefits from technical guidance and performance optimisation tools developed within the project.
Technology and Energy Sector	Hardware and software providers; Energy-efficiency technology companies; Energy companies; ESCOs; Utility companies	These actors contribute to the deployment of innovative energy-efficient solutions and district-level energy management systems integrated into SUPERSHINE demonstrators.
Residents and End Users	Tenants; Consumers; Prosumers	Residents are the ultimate beneficiaries of SUPERSHINE outcomes. Communication activities ensured that benefits such as reduced energy bills, improved comfort, and healthier environments were clearly conveyed, fostering social acceptance and behavioural engagement.
Associations, Clusters and Membership Organisations	Housing associations; National and regional federations; Thematic clusters and European networks	These organisations act as multipliers, facilitating knowledge transfer, replication, and scaling of SUPERSHINE results beyond the demonstrator cities.

Stakeholder Group	Sub-groups	Role and Relevance in SUPERSHINE
Scientific Community and Technical Experts	Academic institutions; RTOs; Independent experts	Dissemination targeted this audience to ensure methodological transparency, scientific credibility, and potential further research development.
Media	National media outlets; European media platforms	Media engagement supported public visibility and reinforced awareness of the social and environmental relevance of social housing renovation.

As the project evolved, maintaining open and structured communication channels with key stakeholders proved essential. Regular feedback loops and adaptive engagement strategies ensured that SUPERSHINE solutions remained relevant to evolving regulatory frameworks, financial conditions and market expectations.

Not all stakeholder groups were equally relevant for each Key Exploitable Result (KER).

Targeted stakeholder engagement maximised impact by recognising the distinct roles, decision-making capacities and information needs of each group. Technical documentation, financial modelling and governance guidelines were tailored to professional audiences, while simplified narratives were developed for citizens and media.

Clusters, partnerships and European networks played a crucial role in amplifying SUPERSHINE’s outreach and strengthening replication potential. Strategic networking activities enabled collaboration opportunities, facilitated peer learning and increased the likelihood of adoption of SUPERSHINE methodologies in additional cities and regions.

3. Online Channels for Communication and Dissemination

Within SUPERSHINE, a comprehensive set of communication and dissemination tools has been developed and implemented to support the objectives of its Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy. Building on the framework and guidelines established in Deliverable D6.1 – Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, and its update in D6.2, the consortium progressively expanded and refined its portfolio of instruments to effectively address different target audiences and communication needs.

3.1. Project Website

The SUPERSHINE website serves as the central reference point for all stakeholders involved in the project and functions as the primary entry point to its objectives, activities and results. It was designed to engage a broad spectrum of target audiences, including social housing organisations, public authorities, the construction and building sector, financial institutions, technology providers, the scientific community and the general public.

The website is fully scalable and has been regularly updated throughout the project lifecycle with fresh and relevant content. All published materials are openly accessible, with no restrictions, and the platform is fully responsive and optimised for access across different devices, including desktop and mobile environments.

In recognition of the strong thematic and operational connection between SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE, both project consortia agreed to optimise resources and maximise impact by sharing a single web platform. Consequently, the existing SUPER-i website was restructured to incorporate dedicated sections for SUPERSHINE.

The updated website includes shared sections for news, events, and resources, while a clear and transparent labelling system was introduced to distinguish content belonging to each project. The homepage was redesigned to prominently represent SUPERSHINE, while maintaining a clear call to action towards SUPER-i, ensuring that visitors can immediately recognise the collaborative framework underpinning the two projects.

Figure 1: SUPERSHINE Homepage

As part of this restructuring process, website texts were carefully reviewed and updated to ensure coherence, clarity and alignment with SUPERSHINE’s objectives, Key Exploitable Results and final achievements. Content was revised to reflect the evolution of the project, the consolidation of results and the strengthened positioning of SUPERSHINE within the European sustainable renovation landscape.

The updates for each section on the website are available in the table below:

Table 2: SUPERSHINE Website updates

Sections		Updates Implemented
General Sections (Homepage, Approach, Outcomes and Results)	About, Key	Content updated and aligned with project progress and final results.
Trieste (Lighthouse)		Updated texts reflecting the redevelopment of Via Boito, including innovative technological and residential solutions. Content highlights improvements in energy performance, environmental sustainability, and liveability of indoor and outdoor spaces. Integration of video and financial graphs provides a comprehensive overview of implementation and outcomes.
Herning (Lighthouse)		Content updated to showcase circular construction and community-led regeneration, including the orangery built from recycled materials and the “Green and Blue Oasis”. Financial graphs and video content have been integrated to illustrate environmental and social impacts. Key elements

Sections	Updates Implemented
	include biodiversity features and active involvement of residents and students.
Riga (Lighthouse)	Updated content focusing on energy efficiency improvements and neighbourhood-scale interventions, supported by financial graphs. The page highlights a comprehensive participation programme and the use of digital tools for inclusive engagement. Existing content has been refined to reflect outcomes and priorities identified through stakeholder input.
Fellow Cities	Texts updated to reflect project developments and local context and integration of financial graphs.
Resources	Inclusion of key project materials, including flyer, roll-up, final publication, and complete factsheets. Content is clearly divided between SUPERSHINE and SUPER-i.

Figure 2: Trieste updated version (First)

Figure 3: Trieste updated version (Second)

Figure 4: Setubal updated version

Figures 2, 3 and 4 above provide a visual representation of the updates.

In addition to the updated content, SUPERSHINE introduced a dedicated Toolkit page on the project website. This section presents the objectives of the Toolkit, the Knowledge Pyramid, and the full set of factsheets produced by ICONS, based on content developed by CARTIF. The materials are organised through a colour-coded structure to facilitate navigation and usability.

Figure 5: SUPERSHINE Toolkit

Figure 6: SUPERSHINE ToolKit

Figure 7: SUPERSHINE ToolKit

Since its launch, the project website has generated a total of 46,389 views, reflecting sustained user interest. A detailed analysis of website performance is presented in the Monitoring section of this deliverable.

3.2. Social Media Channels

SUPERSHINE established a strong and strategically oriented online presence, with LinkedIn serving as the primary social media platform throughout the project duration. Given the project's focus on engaging diverse range of stakeholders including municipalities, social housing providers, financial institutions, investors, technical experts and policymakers LinkedIn was identified as the most appropriate and effective channel for targeted outreach and professional dissemination.

In addition to LinkedIn, a Twitter/X account was initially created as a complementary channel to extend visibility beyond strictly professional audiences. In July 2024, the joint SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE Twitter/X account was suspended due to external platform-related issues.

In response, and to maintain and further expand digital visibility, SUPERSHINE launched an official Facebook page in October 2024. The introduction of this additional channel enabled the project to reconnect with wider audiences and diversify its social media presence, particularly towards community-level and non-technical stakeholders.

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All social media platforms were actively managed and regularly updated with content generated both internally and by consortium partners. Editorial planning ensured alignment with project milestones, key deliverables, events and major achievements. Content included news updates, event announcements, technical highlights, video materials and stakeholder testimonials.

This multi-platform strategy ensured continuous visibility, reinforced stakeholder engagement and supported the dissemination of SUPERSHINE results across different audience segments.

SUPERSHINE’s social media strategy was defined at the outset of the project, aiming to create a natural continuum with the foundation established by the SUPER-i project activities, while also ensuring a clear distinction between the two projects using the project’s hashtag (#SUPERSHINE_EU). LinkedIn was identified as the most effective channel for outreach to professional and industrial. The following section presents an overview of the project’s performance across its main social media channels, including LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube. The project’s social media presence shows a strong performance across both engagement and outreach, with LinkedIn emerging as the leading platform in terms of impact.

Figure 8: Social Media Followers Performance

In terms of audience base, the project has reached a total of 1,224 followers, with the largest share on X (656 followers), followed by LinkedIn (526) and a smaller presence on Facebook (42). The figure below, represents the outreach and engagement that SUPERSHINE has generated during its lifetime.

Figure 9 : Outreach & Engagement

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Looking at engagement (15K total interactions), LinkedIn clearly dominates, accounting for 62.74%, indicating that content published on this platform resonates most effectively with the audience. X (Twitter) contributes 26.20%, while Facebook plays a marginal role.

Similarly, for outreach (115K total reach), LinkedIn again leads with 53.68%, followed by X at 39.21%, demonstrating strong visibility across both platforms, with LinkedIn slightly outperforming in terms of audience reach.

Overall, the data confirms that LinkedIn is the most effective channel for both engagement and outreach, while X remains important for audience size and visibility, and Facebook plays a limited role in the current communication strategy.

3.2.1. Social Media Campaigns

Since the beginning of the project, SUPERSHINE has carried out five social media campaigns to mark international awareness days and key thematic events, as well as an ongoing campaign for video interviews. These campaigns were designed to engage the public, promote sustainability, and highlight the project's contributions to energy efficiency and social housing.

The table below provides an overview of these campaigns:

Table 3: SUPERSHINE Social Media Campaigns

Campaign	Date	Description
#Urbanize4Change	31/10/2023	Joint cross-project campaign launched on the occasion of World Cities Day to promote the role of EU projects in creating a sustainable urban future. The campaign was implemented using the hashtag #Urbanize4Change.
SUPERSHINE Website Launch	December 2023 – March 2024	Campaign aimed at promoting the launch of the SUPERSHINE website, introducing the project's objectives, structure, and Lighthouse pilot activities to target audiences.
SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Dialogues Under the Spotlight	January 2024	Video interview campaign featuring experts discussing green energy investments, energy poverty, and sustainability. Contributions include Riccardo Coletta on alignment with New European Bauhaus principles, and Cristina Davì and Simone Pressacco on implementation in the Trieste pilot.
#Energy4NetZero	June 2024	Campaign aligned with the EUSEW 2024 theme "Net-zero energy solutions for a competitive Europe", promoting initiatives supporting decarbonisation through innovative

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Campaign	Date	Description
		technologies and solutions towards a fair and just transition.
Toolkit Presentation Workshop	January 2026	Campaign aimed at increasing visibility and participation in the Toolkit presentation workshop, part of the SUPERSHINE Capacity Building Programme.

4. Communication and Dissemination Tools

A set of tools and channels has been deployed throughout the project, enabling targeted outreach to key stakeholder groups and facilitating the transfer of knowledge across different audiences.

These tools have been strategically selected to maximise reach, engagement, and accessibility, combining digital platforms, visual materials, and interactive resources.

The following sections provide an overview of the main communication and dissemination tools implemented, highlighting their role in supporting the project's objectives and enhancing the overall impact of its activities.

4.1. Visual identity

The SUPERSHINE visual identity was defined in the earlier Communication and Dissemination deliverables, where the project's branding elements, graphic guidelines and visual positioning were formally established.

Throughout the project duration, all digital and offline communication materials including the website, social media graphics, videos, publications and event materials strictly followed the approved visual identity framework. This ensured consistency, recognisability and professional coherence across all communication channels.

Following the integration of SUPERSHINE within the shared SUPER-i web platform, particular attention was dedicated to preserving SUPERSHINE's visual distinctiveness while ensuring harmonious alignment between the two projects. Graphic elements, colour schemes, typography and layout structures were carefully implemented to maintain brand clarity and avoid ambiguity between project identities.

This consistent application of the visual identity strengthened brand recognition, enhanced credibility and reinforced the strategic positioning of SUPERSHINE within the European sustainable renovation landscape.

The SUPERSHINE visual identity was developed in the early phase of the project and is described in detail in Deliverable D6.1 – Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (Part 1)

4.2. Project Flyer

The SUPERSHINE flyer was developed as part of the project’s communication kit to support outreach and dissemination activities. It provides a concise and structured overview of the project, presenting its objectives, key concepts, and expected impacts in a clear and accessible format.

The leaflet is designed to communicate the core elements of the project to a broad audience, including stakeholders, policymakers, industry actors, and the general public. It highlights SUPERSHINE’s focus on social housing renovation, energy poverty reduction, and the development of replicable, sustainable district models, while also presenting the role of the Lighthouse Cities and the project’s alignment with relevant EU policy frameworks.

The flyer has been used both in digital and printed formats to support dissemination activities throughout the project duration.

A total of 1,000 printed copies of the SUPERSHINE flyer were produced and distributed during project events, workshops, and stakeholder engagement activities, contributing to enhanced visibility and supporting direct outreach to key target groups.

SUPERSHINE Flyer is available on the Resources section of the website.

The cover page and the first page of the flyer is represented in the figure below.

Figure 10: Flyer Cover Page

Figure 11: Flyer Second Page

4.3. Final Project Video

The final video for SUPERSHINE was developed to enhance the visibility, understanding, and uptake of the project’s results. Its production was carried out in Month 31 (May 2025), including on-site filming in the Lighthouse Cities and the collection of inputs from key project partners, while the final version was released in Month 38 (December 2025).

The video combines narrative elements with visual materials from project activities, including demonstration sites and developed solutions, to illustrate the project’s approach to building renovation, energy performance improvement, and sustainability.

It also features interviews conducted in Trieste with project representatives, including Riccardo Coletta, Cristina Davi, and Alessandra Cechet, who provide insights into the project’s implementation, key results, and overall impact. Designed for a broad audience of stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public, the video was used as a central communication tool across dissemination channels and events to enhance visibility and support awareness of the project’s outcomes.

The SUPERSHINE project video is available on the project [YouTube channel](#).

Figure 12: SUPERSHINE Project Video

4.4. Video Interviews

SUPERSHINE, in collaboration with the SUPER-i project, developed an initial video series titled [“SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Dialogues Under the Spotlight”](#) as part of its dissemination activities in January 2024.

In March 2026, the project has produced 5 additional video interviews the details are available in the table below.

All of the video interviews can be found on the project’s [YouTube channel](#).

The following table presents the additional video interviews, followed by a brief description with their views.

Table 4: Video Interviews Overview

Name	Description	Views
Riccardo Coletta (APRE – Project Coordinator)	Presents the overall vision of the SUPERSHINE project, focusing on how it addresses energy poverty through integrated technical, financial, and community-driven solutions.	28
Nadia Vedova (Kallipolis Association)	Explains the participatory co-design approach implemented in the Via Boito district (Trieste), highlighting stakeholder	20

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	engagement processes and the inclusion of vulnerable groups.	
Antonella Trobez (Local stakeholder – Via Boito, Trieste)	Provides a local business perspective on the evolution of the neighbourhood and expectations regarding regeneration and community revitalisation.	15
Mario Sorz (Resident – Via Boito, Trieste)	Shares long-term experience and personal insights on the social transformation of the neighbourhood, reflecting on past conditions and future expectations.	8
Cristina Davi (ATER Trieste)	Describes the role of ATER in the project and its involvement in the Lighthouse intervention, focusing on energy efficiency improvements and resident engagement.	22
Supershine project	The video presents a project study visit to the Øbro 95 demonstration site in Copenhagen, showcasing how energy-efficiency solutions can be effectively integrated into Denmark’s non-profit housing sector.	28

4.5. Editorial Activities

Editorial activities represented a key component of the SUPERSHINE communication and dissemination strategy, supporting the structured and continuous dissemination of project results to a wide range of target audiences. Through a combination of news releases, event releases, press releases, journalistic articles, and newsletters, the project ensured regular visibility and effective communication of its activities, milestones, and outcomes.

4.5.1. Press Releases

Within the SUPERSHINE communication activities, a total of 5 press releases were produced and tracked, including those monitored and additional releases published in March 2026. These press releases supported the promotion of key project milestones, results, and policy-oriented outputs, contributing to the project’s visibility and outreach.

Table 5: SUPERSHINE Press Releases

Date	Title
18/12/2023	A Closer Look into SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Get to know the impact better
10/12/2024	SUPERSHINE Project Holds Field Visit to See Energy Democracy in Action
18/03/2026	SUPERSHINE Policy Brief calls for a “Just Renovation” framework for Europe’s social housing
24/03/2026	SUPERSHINE publishes final results for sustainable and inclusive social housing renovation in Europe
27/03/2026	A New EU Toolkit to Drive Inclusive and Energy-Efficient Building Renovation

A total of 5 press releases were produced, generating 3,109 outreach and 71 engagement interactions, thereby contributing to the project’s overall visibility and stakeholder engagement. The outreach and engagement metrics generated by these outputs feed into the calculation of the Publication Engagement Index (PEI), which is further detailed in the monitoring section.

The press releases were distributed through established media multipliers, including AlphaGalileo, Science X, and EU Agenda, to maximise visibility and generate further awareness of the project and its results.

The outreach and engagement generated by the press releases contribute to the calculation of the Publication Engagement Index (PEI), which will be further explained in the monitoring section.

4.5.2. News Releases

News releases constituted a key component of the SUPERSHINE communication strategy, supporting the timely dissemination of project activities, results, and milestones to a wide range of stakeholders.

Throughout the project duration, a total of **16 news releases** were produced and published on the project website and further amplified through digital channels. These releases covered major events, stakeholder engagement activities, project achievements, and the development of key outputs, contributing to sustained visibility, stakeholder engagement, and the promotion of project results across different phases of implementation.

The table below lists the news releases for SUPERSHINE:

Date	Title	Type	Outreach	Engagement
24/06/2023	SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE at the 4th International Social Housing Festival – Highlights	News release	440	35
01/02/2024	Shaping Tomorrow Together: Surveys for Lighthouse Owners, Managers, Residents, Tenants, and Local Businesses	News release	262	0
15/02/2024	SUPERSHINE Lighthouse Districts: Pave the Way for Sustainable Urban Living	News release	618	34
26/06/2024	SUPERSHINE at Trieste: A New Way of Sustainable Living	News release	723	197
10/07/2024	Updates from Our Lighthouse District: Denmark's Green Innovations in Herning	News release	1,206	115
02/09/2024	SUPERSHINE Joins the Network of Building Renovation Projects	News release	651	43
12/11/2024	FB Launches Pilot Rewilding Project for SUPERSHINE to Transform Green Areas and Engage Local Community	News release	542	45
21/01/2025	Co-Design Workshop: Engaging Youth Through Minecraft for Urban Design in Trieste	News release	329	23
28/01/2025	Young Minds Shape Public Spaces: Co-Design Session in Trieste	News release	2,065	159
22/09/2025	SUPERSHINE at Klimafolkemødet 2025: Dialogue on Energy Poverty and Social Justice	News release	202	17
21/01/2026	Practical Solutions for Energy-Efficient and Inclusive Housing Renovation: Insights from SUPERSHINE's Latest Workshop	News release	203	24
23/02/2026	SUPERSHINE at the BRIDGE Workshop	News release	442	27
09/03/2026	The SUPERSHINE Final Event Brought Together Cities, Experts, and Stakeholders in Riga	News release	608	118
18/03/2025	SUPERSHINE at the NEUTRALPATH Capacity Building Programme – Citizen Awareness and Engagement Strategies	News Release	799	73
15/05/2025	Rethinking the Neighbourhood together	News Release	470	47

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Date	Title	Type	Outreach	Engagement
19/09/2025	SUPERSHINE joins EU webinar spotlighting fair, affordable and energy-smart housing	News Release	155	18
03/10/2025	SUPERSHINE for World Habitat Day 2025	News Release	513	47
20/10/2025	Empowering SMEs through Intellectual Property: SUPERSHINE at the INSME Annual Meeting	News Release	185	15
20/10/2025	Highlights from SUPERSHINE’s Participation at Sustainable Places 2025	News Release	173	30
24/10/2025	SUPERSHINE Wins Herning Municipality’s 2025 Building Award	News Release	204	24
10/11/2025	SUPERSHINE at the Building Change Conference	News Release	164	21
	Total		10,954	1,112

The outreach and engagement generated by news releases contribute to the calculation of the Publication Engagement Index (PEI), which will be further explained in the monitoring section.

4.5.3. Event Releases

In total, 22 event releases were produced throughout the project duration, contributing to the visibility of SUPERSHINE activities and facilitating outreach towards targeted audiences. These event releases highlight both the participation of SUPERSHINE in external events and the events organised within the project.

The table below represent the event releases published by SUPERSHINE:

Table 6: SUPERSHINE Event Releases

Date	Title	Outreach	Engagement
19/05/2023	WORKSHOP: Investments in energy efficiency in public housing	73	0
21/06/2023	New European Bauhaus in Regions and Cities	79	0
09/11/2023	European Week of Regions and Cities	27	0
08/05/2024	Satellite event: climate neutrality in cities	18	0
04/06/2024	New Bauhaus Stories	3	0
13/06/2024	NEB Lighthouse of Trieste Launch event	675	68
14/10/2024	INSME Annual Meeting: Unlocking Sustainable Finance for SMEs	771	111

Date	Title	Outreach	Engagement
06/11/2024	Transforming Social Housing Districts for a Sustainable Future	392	33
26/05/2025	SUPERSHINE joins the drop Final Conference at ISHF	216	29
28/05/2025	C4T Event on Cohesion Policy and Climate Action	141	6
28/05/2025	SUPERSHINE joins the 4th Capacity Building Workshop of the ProLight Project	453	49
29/05/2025	Public Engagement in Social Housing Seminar at ISHF 2025	224	21
21/07/2025	SUPERSHINE Joins the Climate People’s Meeting 2025	364	42
28/08/2025	SUPERSHINE at the webinar on housing inequalities	885	77
29/08/2025	SUPERSHINE at Sustainable Places 2025	588	66
24/10/2025	Building Change: Boosting Innovation for Affordable Housing	149	21
24/10/2025	INNEXA 2025	154	21
17/11/2025	SUPERSHINE Toolkit Workshop	460	67
01/12/2025	Driving the Renovation Wave Together	247	29
01/12/2025	Inclusive Renovation: Tackling Energy Poverty	223	27
12/12/2025	SUPERSHINE invites you to the Toolkit Workshop	2,691	278
25/02/2026	SUPERSHINE Final Event: Save the Date	267	40
	Total	9,100	985

The outreach and engagement generated by event releases contribute to the calculation of the Publication Engagement Index (PEI), which will be further explained in the monitoring section.

4.5.4. Journalistic Articles

In total of 2 journalistic articles were written as part of the SUPERSHINE project to communicate project results and perspectives to a broader audience, beyond the immediate project stakeholders.

These articles contributed to raising awareness on key topics such as energy democracy, social inclusion, and the social dimension of the energy transition.

The table below presents the journalistic articles, their context, and the outreach and engagement generated. The articles were distributed through established media multipliers, including AlphaGalileo, Science X, EU Agenda, and youris, to maximise visibility and reach.

Table 7: SUPERSHINE Journalistic Articles

Date	Title	Context	Outreach	Engagement
02/07/2024	Decentralisation, sustainability and energy democratisation: The untapped potential of citizen-led initiatives	Explores how citizen-led initiatives drive energy democracy and decentralised systems, supporting inclusive and sustainable energy transitions.	19,571	444
11/11/2025	Beyond efficiency: putting the social factor at the heart of Europe’s energy transition	Emphasises the need to integrate social dimensions into energy transition policies, highlighting energy poverty and inclusivity as key priorities.	3,712	93
	Total		23,283	537

4.6. Toolkit and Factsheets

Within the SUPERSHINE project, the Toolkit represents a key output aimed at supporting knowledge transfer and stakeholder uptake. The core content of the Toolkit consists of a set of thematic factsheets, developed by CARTIF, which translate the project’s technical, financial, and social solutions into structured and actionable guidance.

The factsheets were initially developed in structured formats (e.g. Excel and document-based templates) and subsequently transformed by ICONS into visually engaging and accessible formats, aligned with the project’s visual identity. This process ensured that complex content was presented in a clear, user-friendly manner, suitable for a wide range of stakeholders.

ICONS also supported the promotion of the Toolkit by implementing a dedicated social media campaign, (production of the speaker cards and promotion on the projects social media channels) to increase visibility and participation in the workshop organised by CARTIF

Both versions have been made publicly available through the SUPERSHINE website, as part of the dedicated Toolkit section. The Toolkit is also integrated within the project’s online platform, ensuring accessibility and supporting the dissemination, uptake, and replication of SUPERSHINE results.

The table below presents the full set of factsheets designed by ICONS, included in the Toolkit:

Table 8: Factsheets

Category	Factsheet Title	Description
Energy Efficient Buildings	Envelope insulation and enhancement	Explores solutions such as ETICS, high-performance windows, and façade systems to reduce building energy demand.
	Integration of renewables	Focuses on integrating renewable energy systems to achieve low- or zero-energy buildings.
	A new design paradigm	Highlights human-centred and nature-based design approaches aligned with New European Bauhaus principles.
Low Carbon Districts	Urban decarbonisation	Addresses strategies for reducing emissions at district scale through integrated planning.
	Sustainable mobility	Explores low-carbon mobility solutions and their role in district-level sustainability.
	District heating and cooling networks	Focuses on efficient energy distribution systems at district level.
Sustainable Lifestyles	Urban green infrastructure	Highlights nature-based solutions and green spaces to improve urban resilience and wellbeing.
	Energy use: improving behaviours	Addresses behavioural change and user engagement in energy consumption.
Environmental Impact	Life-cycle thinking and circularity	Explores circular economy approaches and lifecycle assessment in renovation processes.
	Waste: end-of-life phase	Focuses on waste management and material recovery strategies.
	Economic aspects of energy actions	Analyses financial feasibility and economic impacts of energy efficiency measures.

ENHANCING BUILDING ENVELOPES TO REDUCE ENERGY DEMAND

ENVELOPE INSULATION & ENHANCEMENT

Improving the building envelope through external insulation (ETICS), high-performance windows, shading devices, ventilated façades, and green/smart façade systems is one of the most effective ways to reduce building energy demand. These interventions address thermal bridging, improve airtightness, enhance summer/winter comfort, and deliver typical energy savings of 20–30%. Envelope upgrades are foundational to achieving EU renovation targets and unlocking further electrification and renewable integration.

TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

Envelope insulation and enhancement strengthen thermal performance and comfort by reducing heat loss in winter and overheating in summer. Measures include ETICS, ventilated façades, window/door replacement, shading, green façades, and smart controls for solar management.

Key technical components include:

- ▶ Insulation materials (EPS, mineral wool, cork) with $\lambda < 0.040$ W/m·K
- ▶ Window performance ($U_w < 1.3$ W/m²·K; low-E double/triple glazing)
- ▶ Thermal bridge correction and airtightness continuity
- ▶ Dynamic shading (fixed/mobile slats, automated blinds)
- ▶ Green façades and smart façades for climate adaptation and comfort
- ▶ Moisture management and vapour-open materials
- ▶ Compliance with building codes, heritage requirements, and energy standards

SCORING

DIFFICULTY

●●●●○

COST OF IMPLEMENTATION

●●●●○

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

●●●●●

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

●●●●●

KNOWLEDGE RECOMMENDATIONS

OVERALL GUIDANCE

- ▶ Prioritise pre-1960 buildings where envelope performance is weakest.
- ▶ Combine insulation with adequate ventilation to avoid moisture issues.
- ▶ Train installers to ensure correct detailing around edges, bridges, and junctions.
- ▶ Select vapour-open systems in humid climates to prevent condensation.
- ▶ Integrate aesthetic improvements and comfort benefits into renovation plans.

POTENTIAL CHALLENGES

- ▶ Unexpected structural issues in older buildings (moisture, cracks, asbestos).
- ▶ Poor installation causing thermal discontinuities.
- ▶ Cost barriers in low-income areas without subsidies.
- ▶ Resistance in multi-owner buildings due to aesthetics or cost-sharing.
- ▶ Higher maintenance needs for green façades and smart automated systems.

ADAPTATION ACROSS CITIES

- ▶ Cold climates: prioritise insulation thickness and airtightness.
- ▶ Warm climates: shading and solar control are critical.
- ▶ Heritage areas: use reversible or visually neutral solutions.
- ▶ Social housing: favour passive, low-maintenance solutions.

Learn more about our solutions in the complete factsheet series on: super-i-supershine.eu

Figure 13: Factsheet Example

KEY CHALLENGES, RISKS, AND SYSTEM GAPS

RECURRENT RISKS

Envelope insulation and enhancement measures involve several recurrent technical and organisational risks. Poor design or execution can lead to condensation, mould formation, and inadequate treatment of thermal bridges, undermining both energy performance and indoor comfort. In older buildings, structural deterioration may only become apparent during construction, increasing costs and causing delays. Budget overruns linked to hidden defects and weak coordination between contractors further threaten timely and effective delivery.

CITY ISSUES

Many cities are characterized by an ageing building stock with insufficient insulation, resulting in high heating and cooling costs and persistent energy poverty, particularly among vulnerable households. Low renovation rates slow down progress toward energy-efficiency targets, while uniform or degraded façades can negatively affect urban quality and architectural value, reducing public acceptance of renovation interventions.

ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

Poor envelope performance contributes significantly to high CO₂ emissions from space heating and cooling. Inadequate insulation and solar control exacerbate urban overheating during summer, while moisture accumulation within building envelopes increases the risk of material degradation and health issues. In dense urban areas, insufficient acoustic insulation also leads to higher noise infiltration, affecting indoor comfort and well-being.

MANAGEMENT GAPS

Implementation is often constrained by limited technical capacity within municipalities and among market actors. The absence of standardised renovation workflows complicates project planning and quality control, while weak enforcement of building codes allows suboptimal solutions to persist. In addition, insufficient and fragmented data on envelope performance reduces the ability to prioritise interventions and monitor results effectively.

OBsolete TECHNOLOGIES

A large share of the existing building stock still relies on outdated envelope components, including old windows with high U-values, uninsulated walls and roofs, inefficient shading devices, and ageing façade finishes. Replacing these obsolete technologies with high-performance solutions is essential to achieve durable energy savings, improved comfort, and long-term building resilience.

PHASES OF IMPLEMENTATION

	P1 – PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS & PLANNING	P2 – CONSTRUCTION & INSTALLATION	P3 – COMMISSIONING & MONITORING
Envelope insulation and enhancement are delivered through a clear, sequential process that moves from technical assessment and design to installation and long-term performance control. This phased approach ensures correct material selection, high-quality execution, regulatory compliance, and durable energy and comfort benefits over time.	<p>P1.1 Building Envelope Audit: conduct thermography, blower door tests, visual inspections, and plan checks to identify losses, thermal bridges, and moisture risks.</p> <p>P1.2 Material & System Selection: select insulation materials, glazing, and shading based on climate, orientation, humidity, and local regulations.</p> <p>P1.3 Legal & Permit Compliance: obtain municipal permits, subsidy applications (NearGen/EU national funds), and heritage approvals where applicable.</p>	<p>P2.1 Surface Preparation: clean façades, repair cracks, remove deteriorated elements, and verify structural resistance for insulation anchoring.</p> <p>P2.2 Insulation System Installation: install ETICS or ventilated façades, apply adhesives, mechanical fastenings, and reinforced render layers.</p> <p>P2.3 Window & Door Replacement: install high-performance units with airtight perimeter sealing and correct thermal break integration.</p> <p>P2.4 Shading & Solar Control Systems: install fixed/mobile shading, automated blinds or façade-integrated solar control solutions.</p>	<p>P3.1 Final Inspections & Testing: conduct airtightness tests, thermographic verification, insulation thickness checks, and shading system calibration.</p> <p>P3.2 User Orientation: provide manuals and training for automated systems and façade maintenance.</p> <p>P3.3 Maintenance Plan: define annual maintenance cycles for façades, windows, shading, and biannual checks for green systems.</p>

Figure 14: Factsheet Example

4.7. Policy Brief

SUPERSHINE developed a policy brief titled “A Just Renovation Framework for Europe’s Social Housing Sector” in March 2026. The policy brief addresses the need to align climate objectives with

housing affordability and social equity, positioning social housing at the core of the energy transition.

The policy brief identifies key challenges affecting the implementation of renovation measures in social housing, including high upfront investment costs, limited access to financing mechanisms, particularly for smaller housing providers, and the risk of “renoviction”, whereby renovation leads to increased rents and the displacement of vulnerable tenants.

Overall, the policy brief underlines that achieving climate-neutral buildings requires an integrated approach that combines technical innovation with social protection and coordinated governance, ensuring that the benefits of the energy transition are accessible to all.

A total of 200 printed copies of the policy brief were distributed during the final event, supporting on-site dissemination and direct engagement with key stakeholders. The digital version is available on the website [Resources](#) section.

Figure 15: SUPERSHINE Policy Brief

4.8. Final Publication

As a key dissemination and exploitation output, SUPERSHINE developed its final publication titled “SUPERSHINE Final Results: Sustainable and Inclusive Social Housing Renovation in Europe”. The publication presents the main results of the project, providing a comprehensive and replicable model for the renovation of social housing across Europe.

The final publication outlines an integrated approach combining technical innovation, financial mechanisms, social inclusion, and citizen engagement. It demonstrates how deep energy renovation

D6.4 – Report on dissemination and communication activities, including impact analysis

can significantly reduce energy consumption and household energy costs, while ensuring affordability and protecting vulnerable tenants.

Based on the implementation in the Lighthouse Cities (Trieste, Riga, and Herring), the publication highlights the effectiveness of combining energy efficiency measures with participatory approaches and circular construction practices. The results show substantial reductions in energy demand and improved living conditions, confirming the viability of the SUPERSHINE model as a scalable and transferable solution.

In addition, the publication emphasises the importance of integrating financial tools, social safeguards, and governance frameworks to ensure that renovation strategies are both economically viable and socially just. It provides practical guidance and evidence-based insights to support policymakers, social housing providers, and other stakeholders in implementing similar approaches. The final publication has been made available in digital format through the [project website](#), ensuring wide accessibility and long-term availability of the project's results.

Figure 16: SUPERSHINE Final Publication Cover Page

Figure 17: SUPERSHINE Final Publication

Figure 18: SUPERSHINE Final Publication

4.9. Newsletters

SUPERSHINE has implemented a series of newsletters to provide regular updates on project developments, results, and key milestones. The newsletter served as a direct communication channel targeting stakeholders, partners, and interested audiences.

The SUPERSHINE newsletter has 42 subscribers, and a total of 6 newsletters have been sent out during the lifetime of the project.

The table below showcases the newsletters of SUPERSHINE:

Table 9: SUPERSHINE Newsletters

Title	Date
SUPERSHINE’s Newsletter	29/05/2025
SUPERSHINE’s Second Newsletter	16/12/2025
SUPERSHINE invites you to the “Tool Kit Workshop”!	07/01/2026
SUPERSHINE: Final Video	02/03/2026
SUPERSHINE Toolkit Edition	30/03/2026
SUPERSHINE Farewell Newsletter	31/03/2026

4.10. Clustering Activities, Sister Projects & Events

4.10.1. Clustering Activities

SUPERSHINE actively participated in clustering activities through its involvement in the Network of Building Renovation Projects, an initiative launched at the beginning of 2024. The network aims to foster collaboration and exploit synergies among EU-funded projects addressing building renovation, with a particular focus on stakeholder engagement within the construction sector and applied sciences.

At the time of reporting, the network brings together 23 Horizon Europe projects, many of which are part of the Built4People Partnership. Through this collaboration, SUPERSHINE contributed to joint communication and dissemination efforts, facilitating knowledge exchange, increasing visibility, and supporting the alignment of project results with broader European initiatives in the field of sustainable and inclusive building renovation.

4.10.2. Clustering activities with sister projects

SUPERSHINE has drOp, ProLight, and SHAPE EU as sister projects. In addition to contributions to joint communication outputs, several collaborative activities were implemented to strengthen synergies, promote knowledge exchange, and increase the visibility of project results.

Furthermore, SUPERSHINE identified DEDALUS and PREFIGURE as a relevant initiative for collaboration, supporting alignment with broader European efforts in sustainable and inclusive building renovation and stakeholder engagement.

The main joint activities are summarised in the table below.

Table 10: Joint Activities

Activity	Project(s) Involved	Date	Description	Contribution / Impact
Participation in ProLight Capacity Building Workshop	ProLight, SUPERSHINE	February 2026	SUPERSHINE contributed to the workshop by presenting its approaches to stakeholder engagement and social housing renovation.	Supported knowledge exchange and dissemination of project methodologies across initiatives.
Joint SUPERSHINE–ProLight Session	ProLight, SUPERSHINE	February 2026	Organisation of a joint session to align project approaches and share	Strengthened collaboration and

Activity	Project(s) Involved	Date	Description	Contribution / Impact
			experiences on implementation and engagement.	alignment between sister projects.
Participation in DrOp Final Conference (ISHF 2025)	DrOp, SUPERSHINE, DEDALUS	2025	SUPERSHINE and DEDALUS participated in the DrOp final conference, contributing to discussions on neighbourhood regeneration and building renovation.	Increased visibility and facilitated exchange of results within the European ecosystem.
Joint Social Media Campaign (PRE-FIGURE)	UN Habitat Day	2024–2025	Implementation of a joint social media campaign to promote building renovation initiatives and increase visibility of EU-funded projects.	Enhanced outreach, strengthened cross-project visibility, and supported coordinated communication efforts.

4.10.3. SUPERSHINE Final Event

The SUPERSHINE project concluded with its Final Event in Riga, bringing together project partners, policymakers, city representatives, and relevant stakeholders to present the main results, tools, and lessons learned from the project.

The event took place at the Riga City Council (Latvia), with the morning session also accessible online.

The morning session presented the key outcomes of the project, including:

- key indicators for sustainable retrofit
- technical intervention assessment methodologies and the SUPERSHINE Toolkit
- innovative financial models supporting social housing renovation
- replication pathways, including Climate City Contracts

The programme also included contributions from the European Commission and the Smart Cities Marketplace, providing insights into policy frameworks and support mechanisms for advancing energy efficiency, affordability, and sustainability in urban contexts.

The afternoon session focused on the Lighthouse Demonstrators, presenting implementation results from the project’s case study cities (Riga, Trieste, and Herring).

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ICONS was responsible for the preparation of the event agenda and, following the event, produced a dedicated news release to support dissemination of the main outcomes. The figure below presents the agenda developed for the Final Event.

Figure 19: SUPERSHINE Final Event Agenda

4.11. Workshops and Webinars

SUPERSHINE actively participated in a range of workshops and webinars, both as a contributor and organiser, supporting knowledge exchange, stakeholder engagement, and dissemination of project results.

Event / Activity	Type	Role of SUPERSHINE	Organised by SUPERSHINE
Driving the Renovation Wave Together: Synergies and Lessons Learned Across EU Projects	Webinar	Participation and dissemination through event release	No
Inclusive Renovation: Reaching Vulnerable Groups and Tackling Energy Poverty	Webinar	Participation and dissemination through event release	No

Event / Activity	Type	Role of SUPERSHINE	Organised by SUPERSHINE
ProLight Capacity Building Workshop (4th Edition)	Workshop	Contribution as guest speaker (Dr. Paola Zerilli, APRE)	No
ISHF 2025 – Public Engagement in Social Housing	Conference / Workshop	Active participation with DEDALUS	No
Sustainable Places 2025 – Building Renovation Workshop	Workshop	Participation and presentation of project activities	No
Webinar on Housing Inequalities: Inclusive Living, Working and Moving	Webinar	Participation and contribution to thematic discussion	No
NEB Lighthouse of Trieste Launch Event	Event / Workshop	Participation and contribution to project dissemination	No
Satellite Event: Climate Neutrality in Cities	Workshop	Participation and knowledge exchange	No
SUPERSHINE Toolkit Workshop	Workshop	Organisation and delivery of capacity building session	Yes
SUPERSHINE Workshop – Practical Solutions for Energy-Efficient and Inclusive Housing Renovation	Workshop	Organisation and dissemination of project results	Yes
INSME Project Meeting – Empowering SMEs through Intellectual Property	Workshop	Participation and dissemination of project results	No
BRIDGE Workshop – Capacity Building, User Engagement and Inclusivity	Workshop	Contribution and presentation of SUPERSHINE approach	No

4.12. Scientific Publications

As part of the SUPERSHINE Open Science approach, activities related to scientific publications, data sharing, and open-access dissemination were initiated during the project, with a focus on key aspects of energy efficiency in social housing, including innovative financing mechanisms such as Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs) and alternative funding schemes.

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Preliminary work carried out within relevant activities from the project partners contributed to the development of knowledge on business models, investment pipelines, and financing strategies for renovation. These activities were intended to support the preparation of scientific publications analysing the effectiveness of financial mechanisms across different European contexts. While the full set of planned peer-reviewed publications has not been finalised within the project duration, the groundwork established provides a basis for future scientific outputs and continued exploitation beyond the project lifecycle.

In line with Open Science principles, SUPERSHINE ensured the availability of key project outputs through open-access channels. Project deliverables, technical reports, and selected materials have been made publicly accessible, supporting transparency and knowledge transfer. In addition, a dedicated Zenodo community has been established to host and preserve project outputs, contributing to long-term accessibility, reuse of results, and alignment with EU open science requirements.

Further open-access materials include datasets (where applicable), technical documentation, and outputs from stakeholder engagement activities. These resources support replication, comparative analysis, and the broader uptake of project solutions.

Overall, the Open Science approach within SUPERSHINE has been implemented through open-access dissemination of project outputs and data, while activities related to scientific publications remain ongoing, with potential for further development beyond the project duration.

A key scientific output was developed in the form of a working paper authored by Paola Zerilli and Ahmed Djeddi, entitled *“Evaluating Deep Energy Renovation Investments in Social Housing: A Bottom-Up Business Model Integrating Social Discount Rate”*. This monograph provides a detailed analysis of financial mechanisms for deep energy renovation, with a specific focus on integrating social discount rates into investment decision-making processes.

5. Monitoring and Impact

This section presents the overall assessment of the communication, dissemination and engagement activities implemented throughout the entire duration of SUPERSHINE. It provides a qualitative and strategic analysis of outreach and engagement performance, highlighting the effectiveness of the adopted approach and identifying key strengths and lessons learned.

SUPERSHINE’s Communication, Dissemination and Engagement activities were continuously monitored through a structured methodology designed to evaluate both visibility and interaction levels across all channels. Monitoring activities focused on digital performance, stakeholder participation in events, content dissemination and audience feedback.

The analysis is based on a proprietary methodology developed by ICONS, as outlined in the paper *“Two new tools for science communication assessment: the Community Engagement Index and Communication Effectiveness Quadrants”* (Folco et al., 2022), enabling continuous monitoring of quantitative outreach and engagement indicators. This approach serves as the primary method for assessing the impact of SUPERSHINE communication and dissemination activities on its target audiences.

ICONS implemented a structured monitoring framework to distinguish between:

- **Outreach**, referring to one-way communication aimed at generating visibility and awareness;
- **Engagement**, referring to two-way interaction and active stakeholder involvement.

Outreach indicators provided insights into the project’s visibility and its capacity to reach target audiences, while engagement indicators measured the level of interest, interaction, and acceptance generated by SUPERSHINE’s communication and dissemination activities.

The SUPERSHINE website backend and data management were handled by EEIP. Consequently, the monitoring of website performance and data analytics was conducted externally through Google Analytics.

However, through the use of the MS Power BI tool¹, SUPERSHINE was able to calculate and monitor both the Publication Engagement Index (PEI) and the Social Media Engagement Index (SEI), supporting a more comprehensive assessment of communication performance.

- **Publication Engagement Index (PEI)**: measures the level of interest in the project’s publications, including both written and audiovisual content, calculated as the ratio of engagement to outreach across all published materials.

¹ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/power-platform/products/power-bi>

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- **Social Media Engagement Index (SEI):** captures the interest generated by social media content, based on the ratio of engagement to outreach across all social media posts.

These indicators are further analysed and presented in the following sections.

5.1. Website Performance

During the lifetime of the project, the website generated a total of 46,000 views and 175,000 recorded events, indicating consistent user activity and interaction with the platform.

The data shows a generally stable level of traffic over time, with regular user engagement across the project duration. Notably, several significant peaks in website views can be observed, corresponding to key project milestones and communication activities, such as major events, publication of results, and the release of new content (e.g. Toolkit, final outputs, and dissemination campaigns).

These peaks suggest that targeted communication and dissemination actions effectively drove traffic towards the website, confirming its role as a central hub for accessing project information and results. The high number of recorded events further indicates active user interaction with the website content, including navigation, downloads, and engagement with resources.

Overall, the website demonstrates a **consistent performance with periodic high-impact moments**, reflecting the effectiveness of the SUPERSHINE communication strategy in directing stakeholders to the platform and supporting the accessibility and uptake of project results.

Table 11: SUPERSHINE Website Traffic Sources

Channel	Sessions
Direct	12,000
Organic Search	4,500
Referral	2,800
Organic Social	1,000
Unassigned	225
Email	37
Organic Video	5

The table below presents the performance of the main landing pages of the SUPERSHINE website.

Table 12: SUPERSHINE Top Landing Pages Performance

Landing Page	Sessions	Active Users	New Users	Avg. Engagement Time
Homepage (/)	6,519	5,044	4,892	37s
/supershine/about	1,108	900	799	36s
/super-i/about	1,082	997	909	33s
/supershine (main page)	1,017	688	623	24s
/supershine/lighthouses/riga	401	367	356	44s
/e-room	338	309	271	53s
/event/world-sustainable-energy-days-2023	328	317	315	27s
/supershine/lighthouses/trieste	265	232	215	16s
/contact	197	189	175	50s

The homepage represents the primary entry point to the website, generating the highest number of sessions (6,519), confirming its central role in attracting users and directing them towards project content.

The About pages (SUPERSHINE and SUPER-i) also show strong performance, indicating a high level of interest in understanding the project’s objectives, structure, and context. This highlights the importance of clear and accessible introductory content in engaging new users.

Content related to the Lighthouse Cities, particularly Riga and Trieste, demonstrates higher average engagement times (up to 53 seconds), suggesting deeper user interaction with location-specific implementation content and real-world results.

The main SUPERSHINE page also shows strong engagement (44 seconds), confirming its effectiveness in presenting key project information.

Overall, the data indicates that users are primarily interested in:

- understanding the project (About pages)
- exploring concrete implementations (Lighthouse pages)
- accessing structured project information (homepage and main sections)

The website will continue to be maintained and updated beyond the project’s conclusion, ensuring long-term accessibility, sustained visibility and continued relevance for municipalities, housing providers, financial actors and other stakeholders interested in sustainable social housing renovation.

5.2. Publications’ outreach and engagement: PEI

The Publication Engagement Index (PEI) is a composite indicator designed to assess both the performance of SUPERSHINE’s editorial outputs, and the effectiveness of the dissemination channels used. Within the PEI framework, *outreach* refers to the number of impressions generated by published content (e.g. website views and visits), while *engagement* captures the level of interaction with that content, including likes, shares, clicks and comments.

Figure 20: SUPERSHINE PEI

As illustrated in the figure below, SUPERSHINE produced a total of **57 publications**, which collectively generated an overall outreach of approximately **50,000** and **4,232 engagement actions**, resulting in a **PEI score of 44**. This value reflects a strong and consistent editorial performance over the monitoring period, supported by a continuous flow of content aligned with key project milestones and dissemination activities.

Figure 21: PEI Outreach and Engagement details

The analysis of outreach distribution (Figure 22) shows that **social media channels accounted for the largest share of visibility (25,242 impressions)**, closely followed by **external multipliers (23,501 impressions)**, while the **project website contributed 1,531 impressions**. This confirms the strategic importance of combining owned and third-party channels, with multipliers such as AlphaGalileo, Science X, EU Agenda, and Youris playing a key role in extending the reach of project content beyond the core SUPERSHINE community.

In terms of engagement, social media channels proved to be the most effective. **LinkedIn emerged as the leading platform, generating 3,356 interactions**, followed by **AlphaGalileo (439)** and **Facebook (264)**. This highlights the complementary role of channels: while multipliers and external platforms maximise visibility, social media particularly LinkedIn are more effective in stimulating active engagement with the content.

Overall, the results confirm the effectiveness of a **multi-channel communication strategy**, where visibility is driven by external dissemination networks and engagement is reinforced through targeted social media activity. This balanced approach supports both broad outreach and meaningful interaction with project stakeholders.

Figure 22: PEI by Publication Type

The analysis of communication formats (Figure 23) highlights clear differences in performance across content types in terms of outreach and engagement.

Journalistic articles emerged as the **highest-performing format**, achieving the greatest levels of both outreach and engagement. Positioned in the upper-right quadrant, articles demonstrate strong visibility combined with high audience interaction, confirming their effectiveness in communicating complex and policy-relevant content to a broad audience.

Video content also shows strong engagement performance, indicating that **visual and narrative-driven formats** are particularly effective in capturing user attention and encouraging interaction, even when outreach levels are comparatively moderate.

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Event releases and news releases demonstrate **balanced but moderate performance**, contributing to consistent visibility and engagement across the project lifecycle. These formats played a key role in maintaining a steady flow of communication aligned with project activities and milestones.

In contrast, formats such as newsletters and press releases show **lower engagement levels**, reflecting their more targeted and informational nature, primarily aimed at specific stakeholder groups rather than broad audience interaction.

Overall, the analysis confirms that:

- **Articles and video content drive the highest engagement and visibility**
- **Event and news releases ensure continuity and consistency**
- **Targeted formats (e.g. newsletters, press releases) support focused dissemination**

The list of all of the SUPERSHINE publications, on which the communication effectiveness quadrants are based, is provided in Section 4.5 – Editorial Activities.

5.3. Social Media Impacts: SEI

The Social Engagement Index (SEI) evaluates the effectiveness of SUPERSHINE’s social media activities in terms of visibility and interaction across its official channels, primarily LinkedIn and Facebook. The index combines outreach indicators (impressions and reach) with engagement metrics (such as likes, shares, comments, clicks, and video views), providing an integrated assessment of social media performance.

Figure 23: SUPERSHINE SEI

As illustrated in the figure below, SUPERSHINE produced a total of **507 social media posts**, generating an overall outreach of approximately **115,000**, **15,000 engagement actions**, and **3,239 video views**, resulting in a **Social Engagement Index (SEI) of 52**.

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This value indicates a **high level of effectiveness in social media communication**, reflecting the project’s ability to not only reach a broad audience but also stimulate meaningful interaction across its channels.

The distribution of followers shows a balanced presence across platforms, with **X/Twitter (656 followers)** and **LinkedIn (526 followers)** representing the main channels, complemented by Facebook (42 followers). Despite a relatively moderate follower base, the project achieved significant engagement levels, demonstrating the effectiveness of its content strategy.

The high number of posts contributed to maintaining a **continuous and consistent communication flow**, while the strong engagement figures highlight the relevance of the content shared. In particular, the inclusion of audiovisual content, reflected in the number of video views, supported increased interaction and user interest.

Figure 24: SUPERSHINE Social Media Trends

The analysis of social media trends (Figure 25) highlights the evolution of posts, outreach, and engagement over the project duration, as well as the growth of followers across channels.

The data shows a consistent publication activity over time, with regular posting contributing to a steady baseline of outreach and engagement. Several notable peaks in outreach and engagement can be observed, corresponding to key project milestones and communication actions, such as major events, release of results, and targeted campaigns.

Periods of increased posting activity are generally associated with higher engagement levels, confirming the effectiveness of maintaining a continuous and structured communication flow.

However, the data also indicates that high-impact peaks are driven not only by frequency but by the relevance and timing of content, particularly when aligned with major project outputs and dissemination moments.

The follower trend demonstrates a steady and continuous growth across all channels, with X/Twitter showing the highest increase over time, followed by LinkedIn. This reflects sustained audience development and increasing visibility of the project within its target communities.

Overall, the analysis confirms that:

- consistent posting supports baseline engagement and visibility
- peak performance is linked to strategic communication moments
- audience growth was progressive and sustained throughout the project.

5.4. Overall Impact Assessment

The final impact assessment confirms that SUPERSHINE's communication and dissemination activities played a central and enabling role throughout the entire project lifecycle, effectively supporting implementation, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge transfer across all phases of the project. The consistently strong performance across the Publication Engagement Index (PEI) and Social Engagement Index (SEI) demonstrates not only the visibility achieved by the project, but also its capacity to generate sustained interest and foster meaningful interaction among key stakeholder groups.

A core strength of SUPERSHINE's communication strategy lies in its ability to engage a diverse stakeholder ecosystem, including policymakers, social housing providers, financial institutions, industry actors, research organisations, and local communities. The differentiated use of channels and content formats enabled the project to tailor its messages to the needs and expectations of these audiences, ensuring both relevance and continuity of engagement. In particular, LinkedIn and media multipliers such as AlphaGalileo, Science X, EU Agenda, and EURACTIV proved effective in extending outreach beyond the project's immediate network, while the project website served as a central access point for structured and technical content.

Communication and dissemination activities were closely aligned with the project's implementation phases, evolving in parallel with SUPERSHINE's technical and operational progress. In the initial stages, communication efforts supported awareness raising and stakeholder positioning around the challenges of energy poverty and social housing renovation. As the project progressed, dissemination activities accompanied the development and validation of technical solutions, financial models, and participatory approaches within the Lighthouse Cities (Trieste, Riga, and Herring), ensuring visibility of intermediate results and practical applications.

In the final phase, communication activities focused on consolidating and promoting key project outputs, including the SUPERSHINE Toolkit, thematic factsheets, policy brief, and final publication. Dedicated campaigns, event releases, and targeted dissemination actions supported the uptake of these results, while the Final Event provided a platform for direct engagement with stakeholders and presentation of the project's main outcomes.

Throughout the project, the availability of structured monitoring tools and performance indicators enabled SUPERSHINE to continuously refine its communication strategy, prioritising high-performing formats such as journalistic articles, event-related content, and audiovisual materials.

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This adaptive and evidence-based approach contributed to sustained engagement levels and ensured the effectiveness of communication actions over time.

In conclusion, the results presented in this deliverable demonstrate that SUPERSHINE’s communication and dissemination activities were strategic, responsive, and closely aligned with project implementation. They significantly contributed to the visibility, understanding, and uptake of project results, while supporting their transferability and replication. The experience gained and insights derived from the monitoring process provide valuable lessons and transferable practices for future EU-funded projects addressing sustainable and inclusive building renovation and the broader challenges of the energy transition.

6. Communication and Dissemination KPI's

	Planned Measure from the Grant Agreement	KPI / Target	Achieved
Visual Identity	Development of project visual identity (logo, templates, brand book)	N/A	Yes
Website	Development of project website as main entry point for results and materials	>10,000 users	Yes 14,747 users 46,389 page views
Social Media	Activation and management of social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, X/Twitter)	>900 followers	Yes 1,174 followers in total
Social Media Campaigns	Organisation of campaigns aligned with EU/global initiatives	≥4 campaigns	Yes 5 social media campaigns have been carried out
Communication Materials	Development of communication kit (flyer, roll-up, presentations, video)	>400 downloads; 500 printed copies	Yes 1,000 flyers were printed and distributed
Editorial Outputs	Production of news releases, press releases, and journalistic articles	≥10 news releases; ≥2 articles	Yes 21 news releases, 2 journalistic articles have been produced
Audiovisual Content	Production of project video and storytelling content	>1000 views	Partially Project video and the video interviews have generated in total of 760 views
Dissemination Outputs	Development of Toolkit and factsheets	Public availability	Yes
Scientific Dissemination	Publications and participation in EU events	>10 events	Yes Participation in 21 events
Policy Outputs	Development of policy brief and final publication	Public availability	Yes
Capacity Building	Organisation of workshops, webinars, and training activities	Multiple events	Yes
Clustering Activities	Collaboration with sister projects and EU initiatives	N/A	Yes

Figure 25: SUPERSHINE C&D KPIs

7. Conclusions

This deliverable has presented a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination activities implemented within the SUPERSHINE project, highlighting the tools, strategies, and actions deployed to ensure effective outreach, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge transfer.

The communication and dissemination activities carried out throughout the project have successfully contributed to achieving the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement and further detailed in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. Overall, the results demonstrate a strong performance across all key areas, confirming the effectiveness of the adopted strategy and its implementation.

All core communication infrastructures were successfully established, including the project’s visual identity and website, which served as the main entry point for accessing results and materials. The website exceeded its target, reaching 14,747 users and generating 46,389 page views, thus confirming its central role in ensuring visibility and accessibility.

Social media activities also performed positively, surpassing the initial target with 1,174 followers across platforms. Five campaigns were implemented (above target), and 507 posts generated an estimated outreach of 115,000 users, around 15,000 engagement actions, and 3,239 video views.

Significant efforts were dedicated to the production of communication and dissemination materials, with a strong focus on ensuring their relevance and usability for the project’s diverse target audiences. The communication toolkit, including a set of thematic factsheets, translates the project’s technical, financial, and social solutions into structured and actionable guidance, supporting replication and uptake.

Key policy and knowledge outputs further strengthened the project’s impact. The policy brief, “*A Just Renovation Framework for Europe’s Social Housing Sector*” (March 2026), and the final publication, “*SUPERSHINE Final Results: Sustainable and Inclusive Social Housing Renovation in Europe*”, provide strategic and operational guidance for the sector. Together with 57 publications, these outputs contributed to an outreach of approximately 50,000 and generated 4,232 engagement actions.

Scientific dissemination and participation in events played a key role in strengthening the project’s visibility and integration within the European ecosystem. SUPERSHINE actively engaged in numerous workshops, webinars, and conferences, both as organiser and contributor, fostering knowledge exchange and stakeholder engagement.

Collaboration with sister projects and related EU initiatives further amplified the project’s impact. In particular, joint activities with DrOp, ProLight, and SHAPE EU, as well as collaborations with projects such as DEDALUS and PREFIGURE, supported synergies, alignment of approaches, and

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cross-project dissemination through workshops, joint sessions, conference participation, and coordinated communication campaigns.

The organisation of the final event in Riga represented a key milestone in the project’s dissemination strategy. Hosted at the Riga City Council and accessible also online, the event brought together project partners, policymakers, city representatives, and relevant stakeholders to present the main results, tools, and lessons learned.

Overall, the vast majority of KPIs were met or exceeded, with only minor deviations that did not significantly affect the overall performance. The results demonstrate strong outreach, meaningful stakeholder engagement, and a solid contribution to the uptake and scalability of project results.

In conclusion, SUPERSHINE’s communication and dissemination activities have successfully maximised the visibility, accessibility, and impact of the project, laying a robust foundation for the continued exploitation and sustainability of its outcomes beyond the project’s duration.